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COMPOSITIONS BASED ON MODIFICATION OF POLYISOPRENE WITH CHLORINATED POLYISOBUTYLENE. OBTAINING A BINARY MIXTURE OF ISOPRENE RUBBER WITH CHLORINATED POLYISOBUTYLENE AND STUDYING THE VOLUME CONSUMPTION OF ALLOYS

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Abstract

As we know, isoprene rubber (SKI-3) belongs to the class of general-purpose rubbers and has high elastic properties, as well as the ability to coexist with other unsaturated rubbers. Along with its positive properties, it has its shortcomings. Thus, cohesive strength and adhesion with cords are low. In order to improve the adhesion of SKI-3 rubber, binary mixtures of it with chlorinated polyisobutylene (CHPI) in different proportions were initially prepared. The rheological properties of the alloys of the prepared binary mixtures under the influence of stresses caused by different temperatures and loads were studied. The purpose of this work is to prepare a composition material based on SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixtures after determining the optimal ratio and processing conditions.

Keywords: isoprene rubber, chlorinated polyisobutylene, binary mixture, rheology, alloy of the mixture.

Introduction

Development of composite materials that meet the requirements of operating conditions plays an irreplaceable role in the development of the industry. Existing polymer-based composite materials do not fully meet the growing demands of the consumer. To meet these growing demands, the synthesis of new high-molecular compounds is not considered viable from the point of view of economic efficiency. At present, the method of modification of existing polymers with compounds with different functional groups (monomer, oligomer, polymer, etc.) is used to obtain composite materials based on polymers that meet the requirements of operating conditions. Rheological (volume consumption) of alloys of the mixture under the influence of different temperatures (100, 120, 150, 178(°)C) and stresses caused by loads (11.75, 20.85, 26.1, 32.6 kg) by preparing binary mixtures of polyisoprene rubber in

different proportions properties are investigated. (Figure 1-4) One of the most important issues in the tire industry is the production of a number of rubber products that can meet the requirements of different operating conditions.

Experimental part

The aim of the study was to determine the properties and fluidity of rubber under the influence of chlorinated polyisobutylene (CHPI), isoprene rubber under different temperatures (100, 120, 150, 178°C) and loads (11.75, 20.85, 26.1, 32.6 kg). and the effect of CHPI on the properties of isoprene rubber-based compositions. For this purpose, isoprene rubber is mechanochemically modified at 45-60°C in a laboratory two roll mixer with a different mass fraction (2-10 k.h.) chlorinated polyisobutylene. (Table 1)

Table 1

		Composition of SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixtures					
N	The code of the mixture						
	Components	1N	2N	3N	4N	5N	6N
1	SKI-3	100	98	96	94	92	90
2	CHPI	-	2.0	4.0	6.0	8.0	10.0
	Sum	100	100	100	100	100	100

Using the IRT-5 device, the flow rates of the obtained SKI-3 / XPIB binary mixtures in the alloy were investigated. At the above temperatures, when the alloys of binary mixtures are spent flowing through a 2 mm long capillary under the influence of loads, we present them in tabular form. (Table 2)

Table 2

The time when SKI-3 / CHPI binary alloys are used to flow through 2mm capillaries (in seconds)

Samples	100°C				120°C			
	Loads, kg				Loads, kg			
	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6
1N	297.39	84.36	40.05	17.13	175.17	38.64	23.75	10.7
2N	92.91	24.14	15.73	8.46	52.88	13.34	8.32	4.44
3N	100.12	26.85	16.20	8.96	52.75	13.02	8.57	4.63
4N	108.85	29.48	16.89	9.09	52.35	12.81	9.10	4.89
5N	141.47	35.97	20.37	12.07	76.38	18.92	11.75	6.25
6N	169.41	40.25	22.17	13.82	83.42	22.51	13.27	8.65
Samples	150°C				178°C			
	Loads, kg				Loads, kg			
	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6	11.75	20.85	26.1	32.6
1N	76.37	18.41	8.37	6.68	36.22	13.37	9.18	4.50
2N	23.04	6.095	3.38	2.2	19.83	5.26	3.26	2.22
3N	24.69	6.38	4.10	2.35	23.60	6.70	4.25	2.57
4N	22.13	5.96	4.30	2.45	29.54	7.96	5.58	2.92
5N	27.39	7.24	4.44	2.33	30.83	8.18	5.99	3.53
6N	28.75	9.12	5.10	2.45	31.75	9.16	6.45	3.84

Results and its discussion

SKI-3 and SKI-3 /CHPI are taken from each of the binary system mixtures in equal amounts (at each temperature) and placed on the cylinder of the viscometer and kept for 4 minutes until the temperature of the chamber is reached. Under the influence of loads, to flow occurs in binary mixed alloys due to relatively irreversible deformation. This is because the macromolecules move relative to each other in the direction of the centers of gravity. When plotting the dependence of Q (volume consumption) on chlorinated polyisobutylene in a binary mixture, it can be seen that the amount of CHPI in the mixture at a temperature of 100 and 120°C

is 2 k.h. the volume consumption of the mixture increases by 2 units under the influence of a load of 11.75 kg compared to SKI-3. In the subsequent increase of CHPI in the mixture, the volume consumption of the mixture alloy decreases monotonically. As the number of subsequent loads increases, the volume consumption of the alloy increases sharply, and the viscosity decreases sharply. When the amount of CHPI in the binary mixture at a temperature of 100°C is more than 2k.h, the volume consumption of the alloy decreases rapidly, the viscosity increases. (Figure 1) Such an increase in viscosity indicates that CHPI plays a role as a filler.

Figure 1.

Volume consumption of SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixture at 100°C depends on the amount of CHPI in the mixture.

The amount of CHPI in the binary mixture SKI-3 / CHPI at a temperature of 120°C is (2-6) k.h. when, the volume consumption of the alloy remains constant un-

der the influence of a load of 20.85 kg, the volume consumption of the mixture alloy rapidly decreases with subsequent increase of CHPI in the mixture (more than 6.k.h.). (Figure 2)

Figure 2.

Volume consumption of SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixture at 120°C depends on the amount of CHPI in the mixture.

Under the influence of loads of 26.1 and 32.6 kg, the volume consumption of the alloy of the mixture decreases rapidly, the viscosity increases. Analyzing the research, it can be concluded that the amount of CHPI in the mixture is 2-6 p.m. under the influence of loads of 11.75 and 20.85 kg, the viscosity of the mixture remains stable, as CHPI interacts with SKI-3 at a constant rate. (Figure 2) When the amount of CHPI in the mixture is more than 6 p.m., the interaction with SKI-3 accelerates and causes structural changes, causing a rapid

decrease in the volume consumption of the mixture. At a temperature of 150°C, the amount of CHPI in the SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixture under the influence of loads of 11.75 and 20.85 kg was 2-6 p.m., the volume consumption of the alloy of the mixture first increases (when it is 2 p.m.) and then remains constant. When the amount of CHPI in the mixture is more than 6.0 p.m., the volume consumption of the mixture alloy decreases sharply, the viscosity increases. (Figure 3)

Figure 3.

Volume consumption of SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixture at 150°C depends on the amount of CHPI in the mixture.

Under the influence of loads of 26.1 and 32.6 kg, the volume consumption of the alloy of the mixture decreases sharply, the viscosity of the system increases.

At a temperature of 178°C, the volume consumption of the alloy of the binary mixture increases sharply, the viscosity decreases when the amount of CHPI in the

binary mixture SKI-3 / CHPI is 2.0 p.m. under the influence of all loads. When the amount of CHPI is more than 2 p.m., the volume consumption of the alloy decreases sharply, ie the viscosity of the system increases, ie it corresponds to the occurrence of a serious vulcanization process. (Figure 4)

Figure 4.

Volume consumption of SKI-3 / CHPI binary mixture at 178°C depends on the amount of CHPI in the mixture.

As a result of research, we can say that by preparing a binary mixture SKI-3 / CHPI (98-94 / 2-6 p.m.) and processing it at a temperature of 145-150°C under a voltage of 11.75, 20.85 kg loads, high adhesion you can buy a capable composition material. On the other hand, when analyzing the graph curves, it can be concluded that the presence of CHPI in the system increases the vulcanization rate of the composition and can reduce the vulcanization time. We will take this into account when developing composition materials based on SKI-3 / CHPI in the future.

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